

The Impact of the Party's Foreign Policy (1965–1975) on the Outcome of the Vietnamese Revolution

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Abstract

The Party's independent and autonomous foreign policy was formed and developed across successive revolutionary periods. During the national democratic revolution (1945–1975), the Party recognised and addressed the challenge of maintaining independence and autonomy in foreign affairs while simultaneously seeking international support and assistance. This approach involved combining national strength with global trends to build a unified force, ultimately leading the Vietnamese revolution to its historic victory in the Spring of 1975, resulting in the liberation of the South, national reunification, and the commencement of a transitional period towards socialism. In the subsequent period of defending independence and initiating reform (1975–1985), the Party's independent and autonomous foreign policy gradually adapted to both global and domestic changes. Moreover, Party thinking evolved significantly, particularly regarding the relationship between independence, autonomy, and international integration.

Keywords: *Foreign policy, Vietnamese revolution, international integration.*

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Introduction

Problem Statement

During the resistance war against US imperialism, the Party thoroughly implemented its foreign policy principles that “the Vietnamese revolution is part of the world revolution,” “Indochina is a single battlefield,” and “helping our friends is helping ourselves.” Defence diplomacy played a particularly vital role in fostering a fighting alliance with the two friendly nations of Laos and Cambodia against the common enemy. To maximise external resources alongside internal strength and create comprehensive power to defeat the enemy, defence diplomacy served as a crucial channel for securing support from the Soviet Union, China, and several other friendly and fraternal

countries. This included the provision of weapons, equipment, logistics, military medicine, and the dispatch of personnel to acquire combat experience and enhance political, military, and tactical knowledge, thus responding effectively to the urgent demands of the revolution.

At the same time, the Vietnamese Army exchanged experience in force building, political and armed struggles, and the art of people's warfare with other national armies, thereby expanding military and defence relations and enhancing Vietnam's international prestige. Through cooperation with other countries, defence diplomacy significantly affirmed the justice of Vietnam's cause, effectively leveraging international solidarity to combine national strength with global momentum. This strategic

combination of forces contributed decisively to the final victory over the invaders, culminating in national liberation and unification.

President Ho Chi Minh's Views on Diplomacy

Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic thought encompasses principles, content, methods, styles, and the art of diplomacy. He promoted fundamental national rights, including independence tied to socialism, national sovereignty, territorial integrity, national unification, peace, and opposition to aggressive wars. He emphasised that diplomacy "must always serve the interests of the nation"; independence, autonomy, and self-reliance must be closely linked with international solidarity and cooperation, asserting Vietnam's readiness to "be friends with all democratic countries and not create enmity with anyone."

Ho Chi Minh highly valued friendship and cooperation with neighbouring countries, sought to expand diplomatic relations across the region and the world, and skilfully managed relationships with major powers to serve revolutionary interests. Diplomacy, he argued, must be a crucial front of the revolution, skilfully combining "fighting and negotiating" and harmonising national strength with global trends to create comprehensive power. He consistently positioned Vietnam within the broader global context, paying close attention to centres of power and major international trends.

He especially emphasised "using the unchangeable to deal with change," maintaining unwavering strategic goals while demonstrating flexibility and adaptability in tactics. His diplomatic method reflected Vietnam's deep-rooted tradition of peace, with an emphasis on resolving disputes through peaceful means whenever possible.

Rooted in national culture, Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style embodies the essence of global cultural values, skilfully blending Eastern and Western traditions. In terms of thinking, he advocated a comprehensive perspective: "look broadly and think carefully" to anticipate global trends and directions of social progress. His behaviour harmonised national and international

values, creating a sense of closeness and trust. In communication, he employed simple language to effectively convey complex diplomatic messages.

A hallmark of his diplomatic art was the adept application of the "five knowledges" — knowing oneself, knowing others, knowing the times, knowing when to stop, and knowing when to change. He demonstrated the ability to create and seize opportunities, practising "diplomacy of the heart" that won people over through justice, humanity, rationality, and morality. The achievements of Vietnamese foreign affairs in national liberation, reunification, and defence clearly illustrate Ho Chi Minh's masterful application of diplomatic arts.

Independence, self-reliance, and international solidarity were key pillars of his diplomatic philosophy. Ho Chi Minh asserted that "Independence means that we control all our own affairs, without any outside interference." He integrated Marxist-Leninist doctrine with Vietnam's historical conditions and the global context, maintaining that "If we want others to help us, we must first help ourselves." Independence and self-reliance, he stressed, were the "root and key" of all problems.

Even during periods of serious discord between the Soviet Union and China, Vietnam's commitment to independence and international solidarity enabled it to maintain strong relationships with both powers and secure significant support. This principle of balancing independence with solidarity guided all of Vietnam's international activities during the Ho Chi Minh era.

Combining national strength with the strength of the times was another crucial strategy. The strength of the Vietnamese people — drawn from geography, politics, culture, and diplomacy — was a synthesis of traditional and modern elements. When combined with contemporary global movements, this national strength was multiplied. Early on, President Ho Chi Minh advocated "making more friends, fewer enemies" and promoted the idea that "Anyone who makes revolution in the world is a comrade of the Anamese people," while stressing the

need to "seek friends and allies even among those who are unstable or conditional."

By enhancing national strength, Vietnam was better positioned to leverage the strength of the times, weakening hostile forces and bolstering revolutionary momentum.

Prioritising friendly and cooperative relations with neighbouring countries was another key diplomatic approach. From the early stages of the revolution, Ho Chi Minh sought solidarity with China's revolutionary forces and advocated cooperation among the three Indochinese countries in the fight against common enemies. He emphasised that "helping the people of a friendly country means helping ourselves."

Ho Chi Minh skilfully navigated international relations, achieving peace agreements when necessary to consolidate revolutionary achievements. For instance, he "made peace with Chiang, fought the French," and later "made peace with the French, pushed Chiang aside." With major powers of opposing ideologies, he consistently aimed to avoid direct confrontation, following the motto: "turn big problems into small ones and small problems into nothing." Wherever possible, he sought peaceful negotiations to resolve conflicts.

Diplomacy as a front line became a defining characteristic of Vietnam's revolutionary strategy. Since the early 20th century, Vietnamese diplomacy had been seen as a vital front line, working in close coordination with political and military struggles. Ho Chi Minh advocated for the strategy of "fighting and negotiating simultaneously," ensuring that the enemy faced resistance everywhere, at all times.

The effectiveness of diplomacy, he noted, depended on the strength of the nation, famously stating that "real strength is the gong, diplomacy is the sound; the louder the gong, the louder the sound." Throughout the resistance wars against French colonialism and American imperialism, diplomacy played a decisive role. The final victory against the US was achieved not only through military might but also through skilful diplomatic efforts.

The Party's Foreign Policy from 1965 to 1975

In early 1965, the United States deployed expeditionary forces to South Vietnam and escalated its war of destruction in the North. On 22 March 1965, the National Liberation Front of South Vietnam issued a five-point statement, declaring:

"The heroic people of South Vietnam are determined to expel the US imperialists, liberate the South, establish an independent, democratic, peaceful, and neutral South Vietnam, and advance towards national reunification."

In order to coordinate action across all forces, secure broad sympathy, garner international support, and strengthen the resistance against the United States, the National Liberation Front convened an extraordinary congress in August 1967. At this congress, it adopted a political platform comprising four major parts, asserting:

"The National Liberation Front of South Vietnam pursues a foreign policy of peace and neutrality, upholding the country's independence, sovereignty, unity, and territorial integrity, while contributing to world peace."

Implementing its strategy of intensifying diplomatic offensives, the Front issued a "Declaration on a Political Solution for South Vietnam" on 3 November 1968. This five-point declaration reiterated the Front's commitment to achieving independence, democracy, peace, neutrality, and prosperity, ultimately leading to national reunification. It affirmed that the internal affairs of South Vietnam must be resolved solely by its people, based on the Front's platform and free from foreign interference. Reunification was to be pursued step-by-step, through peaceful means, again without external intervention. The Front also reaffirmed its foreign policy of peace and neutrality, rejecting any form of military alliance with foreign powers while fostering friendly relations with all countries.

Throughout this period, the Front demonstrated flexibility in adjusting its foreign policy to changing historical circumstances, while remaining steadfast in its strategic objective of

promoting peace and neutrality. This adaptability was reflected in key documents such as the Manifesto and Ten-Point Action Programme (1960), the Five-Point Statement (1965), and the Political Platform (1967).

Numerous delegations of the National Liberation Front attended international conferences in the Soviet Union and China. The Front became an official member of the Afro-Asian People's Solidarity Organisation and signed a Joint Declaration with its Soviet branch, while also establishing representative offices in multiple countries. Prominent international organisations such as the World Federation of Trade Unions, the World Federation of Democratic Youth, and the International Association of Democratic Lawyers, along with the Chinese government, issued statements condemning the US's "special war" and its acts of aggression against South Vietnam.

By 1965, delegations from the National Liberation Front had visited and participated in commemorative events in over 50 countries. In the first eleven months of 1965 alone, 31 delegations travelled to 24 different nations. Between 1961 and 1967, the Front dispatched 139 delegations to international, regional, and national conferences, while 191 delegations of Southern Vietnamese people visited 67 countries, including 12 socialist states, 52 capitalist states, and 3 non-aligned nations. From 1966 to 1967 alone, 65 delegations participated in a range of international forums. These diplomatic activities were instrumental in isolating the United States, weakening enemy alliances, and consolidating support among nationalist, democratic, socialist, and peace-loving forces worldwide.

From 1970 onwards, the Front intensified its global engagement, conducting diplomatic missions to socialist, African, and European nations. Notable visits included Bulgaria (April 1971), Mongolia (June 1971), Cuba (July 1972 and December 1975), the Soviet Union (March 1973), Algeria (September 1973), the liberated zone of Laos (May 1974), Iraq (December 1974), and Yugoslavia (October 1975). The Front also participated in major international events, such as the Fourth Summit of Non-Aligned Countries

in Algeria (October 1973). During these missions, the Front consistently denounced US imperialist aggression and highlighted the victories of the Southern Vietnamese army and people.

The Front was invited to participate in significant events hosted by various countries, such as the congresses of the Communist Parties of France, the Soviet Union, Czechoslovakia, Bulgaria, and Mongolia. Through these engagements, the international community gained a clearer understanding of the Front's objectives, which aligned with the broader aspirations of global movements advocating for peace, freedom, and justice, thereby bolstering support for Vietnam's struggle.

Moreover, representatives of the Front were elected to leadership positions in international organisations. By 1965, Front-affiliated bodies were members of ten international organisations and held executive positions in nine of them. The Fourth Afro-Asian People's Solidarity Conference, held in Ghana in May 1965, issued a resolution recognising the National Liberation Front as the sole legitimate representative of the South Vietnamese people..

The Application of Foreign Policy in Contemporary Nation-Building and Defence

Building on the tradition and identity of Vietnam's diplomatic legacy, while selectively embracing the cultural achievements and progressive ideals of the modern world, the Party and President Ho Chi Minh creatively applied the fundamental principles of Marxism-Leninism. Together, they developed a distinctive and uniquely Vietnamese school of foreign affairs and diplomacy, often symbolised by the image of the "Vietnamese bamboo" — "with firm roots, a strong trunk, and flexible branches." The diplomatic philosophy of the Ho Chi Minh era embodies the spirit, character, and temperament of the Vietnamese people:

soft and skilful yet resilient and decisive; flexible and creative yet steadfast and courageous in the face of hardship; united and humane, yet unwavering and persistent in defending national interests.

First, Vietnam consistently upholds a defence-oriented foreign policy aimed at preserving national independence and self-reliance. While the country remains grateful for the sincere cooperation and support received from the international community during its struggles for national liberation and development, it firmly maintains a spirit of independence and self-determination, relying primarily on its own strength. Vietnam's defence diplomacy strictly adheres to the "Four No's" principle:

1. No participation in military alliances;
2. No alignment with one country against another;
3. No foreign military bases or use of Vietnamese territory against other states;
4. No use of force or threat of force in international relations.

Second, Vietnam consistently pursues a policy of diversification and multilateralism in its foreign relations. The Party and State are committed to cultivating friendships with all countries, prioritising good-neighbourly relations and expanding diplomatic ties regionally and globally. In its dealings with major powers, Vietnam adopts a policy of "not taking sides," firmly placing national interests, independence, and self-reliance at the forefront of its international engagements. By diversifying partnerships and expanding multilateral relations, Vietnam seeks to mobilise international resources and garner broader support for its national development and defence objectives.

Third, Vietnam's defence diplomacy is characterised by a strategy that is *soft and skilful, yet resilient and resolute*. This approach is reflected in efforts to deepen ties with neighbouring countries, maintain a balanced relationship with major powers, and strengthen connections with traditional allies. Vietnam actively participates in multilateral military and defence forums, organises border defence friendship exchanges, and engages in United Nations peacekeeping operations, all of which contribute to enhancing the country's international stature and the reputation of its armed forces.

Fourth, Vietnam's defence diplomacy exemplifies a spirit of strategic wisdom —

understanding the times, knowing the situation, knowing oneself and the adversary, knowing when to advance and when to retreat, and adapting flexibly to circumstances.

The country's consistent policies and diplomatic goals are clearly articulated in the *Vietnam National Defence White Paper*, which emphasises building and strengthening exchange and cooperation with the armed forces of other nations based on principles of equality and mutual understanding.

Conclusion

In the foreseeable future, the global and regional political and security landscape is expected to continue evolving in a complex and unpredictable manner, characterised by heightened risks and instabilities. The cause of building and defending the socialist Fatherland will encounter both new opportunities and significant challenges, placing increasingly higher demands on defence diplomacy. Major powers are likely to intensify strategic adjustments and engage in fierce competition. Armed conflicts and territorial sovereignty disputes are expected to persist, exerting wide-ranging impacts on many countries.

At the same time, the struggle to safeguard national sovereignty and territorial integrity will continue to face considerable difficulties and challenges. Hostile and reactionary forces have not abandoned their strategy of "peaceful evolution" aimed at undermining the Vietnamese revolution. Moreover, non-traditional security threats — including natural disasters, environmental degradation, water security issues, cyber security risks, transnational crime, and terrorism — are presenting new and complex challenges to Vietnam's national defence. These circumstances demand stronger international cooperation and comprehensive diplomatic efforts to effectively address emerging threats and to safeguard national interests.

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